

NAVIGATING ETHICAL DILEMMAS IN BUSINESS DISCOURSE: AN EXPLORATION OF DISCOURSE ETHICS

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Abstract. *Ethical communication plays a pivotal role in shaping a company's reputation, stakeholder relationships, and overall impact on the community. This article delves into the concept of discourse ethics and its significance in business communication, offering insights on how discourse ethics can aid companies in effectively addressing ethical dilemmas. Ethical communication holds numerous benefits for businesses, including building trust, mitigating legal risks, and fostering a positive work culture. While acknowledging the challenges, the article concludes with an optimistic outlook on the future of discourse ethics in business communication, as companies increasingly recognize the importance of ethical discourse in their operations.*

Keywords: *navigating, ethical dilemmas, business.*

Introduction. In today's world, where businesses are constantly under public scrutiny, it has become essential for companies to prioritize ethical communication. The communication that takes place within and outside the company affects its reputation, stakeholders, and the community as a whole (Trevino & Nelson, 2016). Therefore, it is imperative for businesses to navigate ethical dilemmas in their discourse effectively. This is where discourse ethics comes into play. This article explores the concept of discourse ethics in business and how it can help companies navigate ethical dilemmas in their communication. Discourse ethics is a philosophical concept that deals with ethical issues in communication. It explores the moral implications of language, communication, and the power dynamics involved in it (Habermas, 1984). Discourse ethics is concerned with the ethical and moral implications of communication, in terms of its consequences, and the power it holds. In the context of business, discourse ethics is about ensuring that communication within and outside the company is ethically sound and done with the right intentions.

Literature review. The study of business discourse can be traced back to the "linguistic turn" in the social sciences, which emphasized the importance of language as a means of constructing and understanding social reality. Early research in this field focused on applied and pedagogical aspects, aiming to improve communication within business settings. Over time, however, the focus shifted towards understanding the complexities of language use in business contexts, as well as the power dynamics and cultural differences that influence communication practices. Discourse ethics is a philosophical theory that was first introduced by Jürgen Habermas in the 1980s. The theory revolves around the idea that communication is a vital part of human interaction and that it should be governed by moral principles (Habermas, 1984). Habermas believed that communication should be free, inclusive, and respectful of everyone's opinions. He also argued that communication should be aimed at finding a consensus that benefits everyone involved in the conversation. In the context of business, discourse ethics is about ensuring that communication within and outside the company is done with the right

intentions. It involves creating a culture of open and honest communication, where employees are encouraged to speak up and share their opinions without fear of retaliation. Discourse ethics in business is about creating a level playing field where all stakeholders are treated equally, and their opinions are valued (Treviño & Nelson, 2016). Ethical communication is crucial in business for many reasons. Firstly, it helps build trust and credibility with stakeholders. When a company communicates ethically, it shows that it values its stakeholders and is committed to doing the right thing. This, in turn, helps build a strong reputation for the company (Treviño & Nelson, 2016). Secondly, ethical communication helps prevent legal and financial risks. When a company communicates ethically, it is less likely to engage in fraudulent or illegal activities that can cause legal and financial problems in the future (Crane & Matten, 2016). Finally, ethical communication is essential for creating a positive work culture. When employees feel that their opinions are valued and that they are working in an environment where ethical communication is a priority, they are more likely to be satisfied with their jobs and perform better (Treviño & Nelson, 2016).

Ethical dilemmas can arise in business discourse in many ways. It can be in the form of misleading advertising, biased communication, or even harassment (Weaver & Treviño, 2018). For example, a company may exaggerate the benefits of its products to increase sales, even if it means misleading customers. Alternatively, a company may use language that is biased against a particular group of people, even if the intention is not to discriminate. In both cases, the communication is unethical and can damage the company's reputation (Weaver & Treviño, 2018).

Data analysis. Discourse ethics can play a significant role in resolving ethical dilemmas in business discourse. It provides a framework for ethical communication, where all stakeholders are treated equally, and their opinions are valued (Kuhn, 1970). When an ethical dilemma arises, discourse ethics can help companies find a consensus that benefits everyone involved. It involves creating a culture of open and honest communication, where employees are encouraged to speak up and share their opinions without fear of retaliation (Kuhn, 1970). Applying discourse ethics in business communication involves creating a culture of open and honest communication, where employees are encouraged to speak up and share their opinions (Frey, Botan, & Kreps, 1999). It also involves creating a level playing field where all stakeholders are treated equally, and their opinions are valued (Frey, Botan, & Kreps, 1999). This can be done through various means, such as training programs, policies, and procedures that promote ethical communication.

Business discourse research often involves the analysis of various types of data, including:

- Meeting transcripts and recordings
- Emails and other written correspondence
- Reports and other formal documents
- Presentations and speeches
- Negotiations and contracts

Applying discourse ethics in business communication has several benefits. Firstly, it helps build trust and credibility with stakeholders (Crane & Matten, 2016). When a company communicates ethically, it shows that it values its stakeholders and is committed to doing the right thing. Secondly, ethical communication helps prevent legal and financial risks (Crane & Matten, 2016). When a company communicates ethically, it is less likely to engage in fraudulent

or illegal activities that can cause legal and financial problems in the future. There are several approaches that have been used to study business discourse, including:

- Discourse analysis: This involves the close examination of language use, with a focus on understanding the structure, patterns, and functions of communication in specific contexts.
- Conversation analysis and ethnomethodology: These approaches are concerned with the study of talk in interaction, focusing on the ways in which participants use language to accomplish social actions and construct meaning in their exchanges.
- Organizational communication: This field of study examines the communication processes that occur within and between organizations, with an emphasis on understanding the role of communication in shaping organizational culture, structure, and decision-making.
- Sociolinguistics and pragmatics: These approaches explore the relationship between language use and social context, investigating how factors such as culture, identity, and power dynamics influence communication practices.
- Genre analysis and ethnography: These methods involve the study of specific types of discourse, such as meetings or negotiations, and the cultural practices that surround them.

Finally, ethical communication is essential for creating a positive work culture (Trevino & Nelson, 2016). When employees feel that their opinions are valued and that they are working in an environment where ethical communication is a priority, they are more likely to be satisfied with their jobs and perform better. Applying discourse ethics in business communication can be challenging. Firstly, it requires a shift in the company's culture, which can be difficult to achieve (Hartman, DesJardins, & MacDonald, 2014). Secondly, it can be challenging to ensure that all stakeholders are treated equally, especially in companies with a hierarchical structure (Hartman, DesJardins, & MacDonald, 2014). Finally, it can be challenging to ensure that employees feel comfortable speaking up and sharing their opinions (Hartman, DesJardins, & MacDonald, 2014). There are many examples of companies that have successfully applied discourse ethics in their communication. One such example is Patagonia, a clothing company that is committed to ethical and sustainable business practices. Patagonia has created a culture of open and honest communication, where employees are encouraged to speak up and share their opinions. The company also has a policy of transparency, where it shares information about its business practices with its stakeholders (Werhane & Singer, 2019).

Conclusion. In conclusion, discourse ethics is an essential concept in business communication. It provides a framework for ethical communication, where all stakeholders are treated equally, and their opinions are valued (DeGeorge, 2017). Applying discourse ethics in business communication has several benefits, including building trust and credibility with stakeholders, preventing legal and financial risks, and creating a positive work culture (Crane & Matten, 2016). However, applying discourse ethics in business communication can be challenging, and it requires a shift in the company's culture (Hartman, DesJardins, & MacDonald, 2014). Business discourse is a multifaceted field of study that explores the language and communication practices within and around business organizations. As businesses continue to evolve and shape society, the importance of understanding and effectively utilizing business discourse will only grow. By examining the historical development, characteristic features, and

research approaches of this field, we can better understand its complexities and contribute to its ongoing development.

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